

EFFECT OF SQUEEZE INFILTRATION SPEED ON INFILTRATION QUALITY AND TENSILE PROPERTIES OF CAST SAFFIL/ALCU4MGAG COMPOSITE

S. Long¹, O. Beffort¹, L. Rohr¹ and H. M. Flower²

¹ Swiss Federal Laboratories for Material Testing and Research, CH-3602 Thun, Switzerland

² Department of Materials, Imperial College, London SW7 2BP, UK

SUMMARY: In the present work, the effects of squeeze infiltration speed on infiltration pressure gradient, preform saturation, air entrapment and the associated infiltration quality have been theoretically analysed in the light of visualised melt flow behaviour in Saffil chopped fibre preform and the established infiltration hydrodynamics, and empirically investigated by tensile test and microscopy of Saffil/AlCu4MgAg composite infiltrated with systematically varied infiltration speed. It has been found that an increase in infiltration speed gives rise to infiltration pressure gradient and preform saturation. Consequently, the amount of the air entrapped in the preform is decreased and the tensile properties of the fibre casting are improved. It has been concluded that infiltration speed should be maximised within the limit of preform compression strength to achieve quality squeeze infiltration in the atmosphere.

KEYWORDS: metal matrix composite, liquid metal infiltration, Saffil preform, squeeze casting, AlCuMgAg alloy, infiltration processing, tensile properties

INTRODUCTION

To meet the growing requirements for high specific properties of engineering structural materials at room and elevated temperature, intensive research interest has been devoted to incorporate high strength ceramic fibres in light matrix alloys to produce fibrous metal matrix composites (FMMCs). Among the processes developed for fabrication of FMMCs, liquid metal infiltration of fibre preforms aided by external pressure has been attracting a share of research and commercial attention due to the advantages provided by the well-developed casting techniques, such as, cost-effectiveness, potential of net-shape production, processing design versatility and production scale flexibility.

Attainment of satisfactory microstructures and mechanical properties is the ultimate destination of processing research for fabrication of engineering materials. Unfortunately, the wide divergence of processing parameters employed in the infiltration practice, the scattering and, sometimes, discouraging mechanical performance of the cast FMMC materials, and the contradictory interpretations of the observations indicate that the physical nature behind pressurised liquid metal infiltration of fibrous reinforcement preforms for fabrication of cast FMMC engineering structures has not been comprehensively understood and the infiltration

processing design has not been properly related to the formation of microstructure and mechanical properties yet despite that some very good work has been done [1].

According to the nature of pressurised liquid metal infiltration processing, the formation of the microstructure of the fabricated cast FMMC structures is largely co-determined by the physico-chemical interplay between melt flow and the preform consisting of fibres and fibre binder. Achievement of quality infiltration of a chopped fibre preform in the atmosphere relies first on a scientific manipulation of infiltration hydrodynamic parameters, mainly, infiltration speed and pressure, to optimally control the melt flow in the preform and the accompanying air retreat. Based on a quality infiltration, the melt solidification can be regulated to develop desired fibre-matrix bonding, uniform microstructural and phase constitutions.

In the present work, efforts have been contributed to theoretically analyse the effect of squeeze infiltration speed on infiltration quality in terms of infiltration pressure gradient, preform saturation and air entrapment based upon the visualised melt flow behaviour in Saffil preforms and the established infiltration hydrodynamics [2, 3]. Empirically, Saffil preforms have been squeeze infiltrated with AlCu4MgAg melt under systematically varied infiltration speed and optimal thermal parameters. The fabricated material was mechanically and microscopically characterised to visualise the effect of infiltration speed.

Following the procedure of infiltration, melt solidification can take place during and post melt infiltration of the preform. It has been made evident that the melt solidification prior to completion of infiltration, the so-called premature melt solidification, will alter the features of infiltration hydrodynamics and degrade the infiltration quality [4]. Therefore, the theoretical analysis of infiltration hydrodynamics and empirical investigation in the present work are based on the infiltration free of premature melt solidification.

INFILTRATION HYDRODYNAMICS AND INFILTRATION QUALITY

Melt Flow Behaviour in a Chopped Fibre Preform

To correlate the nature of melt flow during infiltration to microstructure formation, it is essential to be aware of the melt flow behaviour in a chopped fibre preform.

Fig. 1 gives the visualised flow behaviour of Al alloy melt in a 28% Saffil preform under squeeze pressurisation. As indicated by its morphology, the melt flow in the fibre preform is dominated by the non-wetting of the melt to the fibres partially coated with SiO₂ binder and the dimensional non-uniformity of the interspaces between the fibres. Under the drive of the external pressure, the melt preferentially penetrates into the interconnected large interspaces at micro scale and, then, penetrates the small ones when the local infiltration pressure increases up to the capillarity of the interspaces in question. Behind the infiltration front, with the increase in infiltration pressure, more and more smaller interspaces are infiltrated, which gives rise to the preform saturation and the associated infiltration quality in terms of non-infiltration interspaces.

Fig. 1 The morphology of the micro infiltration front formed during unidirectional infiltration of a Saffil preform with Al alloy melt. Note the non-uniformity of fibre distribution in the preform, the non-wetting nature of melt to Saffil fibres, the preferential penetration behaviour of melt into the large interspaces between the chopped fibres, and the variation of the preform saturation by the melt flow in infiltration direction [2]. The arrow indicates the macro infiltration direction.

Infiltration Speed and Infiltration Pressure Gradient

According to the visualised melt flow behaviour and the principles of hydrodynamics, statistic analysis of the effect of the dimension of the infiltrated interspaces, ranging from their maximum value $R_{eq,max}$ to the minimum $R_{eq,P}$, and their orientation D on melt flow in individual interspaces leads to the relationship between infiltration speed in terms of squeeze ram speed V_{ram} , and the local pressure gradient dP/dz in the infiltration direction z as follows

$$\frac{dP}{dz} = \frac{A\mu V_{ram} R_{eq,max}^3}{D(1-V_f)(R_{eq,max}^5 - R_{eq,P}^5)} \quad (1)$$

Where, μ is the dynamic viscosity of the matrix melt, A a constant determined by the infiltration system, and V_f preform fibre volume fraction [3].

This equation shows that under a prescribed infiltration speed, the pressure gradient in the infiltrated preform is inversely proportional to $(R_{eq,max}^5 - R_{eq,P}^5)$, indicating the sensitive nature of infiltration pressure to the change of the dimension of the newly infiltrated interspaces. According to the melt flow behaviour and the $P - R_{eq,P}$ relationship presented in Eq. 1, the infiltration can be described as a three stage process as follows.

- 1). *Initiation of Infiltration:* Infiltration of a preform is initiated when the squeeze pressure is increased up to the minimum capillarity resistance of the largest interspaces between the fibres, corresponding to $R_{eq,P}$ close to $R_{eq,max}$. Due to the limited conducting area of the preferentially penetrated large interspaces but the constant melt flux regulated by squeeze ram speed, the melt flow through the first penetrated interspaces is much higher than the average speed and, correspondingly, the resistance of the preform to melt flow increases dramatically. As a consequence, infiltration pressure increases dramatically to

maintain the constant melt flux regulated by the pre-selected squeeze infiltration speed. The increase in pressure endorses the melt higher penetrating capability, resulting in reduced dimension of infiltrated interspaces and, thereby, decreased melt flow speed. This initial stage of infiltration finishes when the dimension of the newly penetrated interspaces $R_{eq,P}$ decreases down to $0.5R_{eq,max}$ and the infiltration pressure becomes stable and proportional to the further increase in infiltration depth.

- 2). *Stable Infiltration:* After the dimension of the newly infiltrated interspaces becomes smaller than $0.5R_{eq,max}$, the further increase of infiltration depth brings proportional increase of infiltration pressure that is required to overcome the melt viscosity and to maintain the constant melt flux until the infiltration front reaches the base of the preform. However, it must be realised that the unstable P - z features of the initial infiltration stage exists in the infiltration front throughout the stable infiltration stage.
- 3). *Compression of Entrapped Air:* As the infiltration front reaches the base of the preform and seals the venting ducts, the air pre-existing in the un-infiltrated interspaces is entrapped and the infiltration enters its air compression stage. Due to the limited amount of the air entrapped and the constant ram displacement, the stage of the air-compression is characterised by its rapid pressure increase until its value reaches the pre-selected maximum infiltration pressure.

According to the above descriptions, the infiltration pressure--infiltration depth relationship ($P_{inf} - z$) throughout the whole infiltration process can be schematically summarised as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 A schematic showing the variation of infiltration pressure with respect to ram displacement during unidirectional infiltration of a Saffil preform. Where, $P_{cap.min}$ --minimum pressure required for initiating infiltration, P_{pr} --pressure for melt penetrating-through the preform with prescribed processing conditions.

It is important to realise that the infiltration pressure is dominated by the infiltration speed in the conventional squeeze infiltration practice, where the infiltration speed represented by ram,

or plunger speed is pre-selected. The infiltration pressure is a automatic response of the hydraulic system to all the resistance of the preform to the melt penetration at the constant flux regulated by the ram speed. Therefore, for a prescribed melt-preform system, only the infiltration speed can change the P - z relationship.

Infiltration Pressure Gradient and Preform Saturation

As indicated by the above brief description, the squeeze pressurised infiltration in the atmosphere is characterised by the existence of an air entrapment stage that can severely affect the infiltration quality. Therefore, it is important to understand the relationship between the intensity of air entrapment and the infiltration hydrodynamics to co-relate the melt flow behaviour to the geometrical features of the fibre preform and the infiltration speed employed.

Due to the kinetic non-wetting nature of the Al alloy melt to the Saffil fibres, the penetrating ability of the melt into the interspaces between the fibres is regulated by the capillarity laws and the local infiltration pressure applied. If an equivalent radius defined as R_{eq} is proposed as a geometrical measurement of an interspace with geometrical irregularity between fibres in the preform, the infiltration pressure P_{inf} required to penetrate such an individual interspace can be given as follows if the melt-fibre kinetic contact angle is suggested as θ and the surface tension of the melt is σ_{mg} .

$$R_{eq} = \frac{\sigma_{mg} \cos \theta}{P_{inf}} \quad (2)$$

Due to the nature of preferential penetration of the melt flow into large interspaces, the degree of saturation of the preform $S(P_{inf})$ under a local infiltration pressure P_{inf} is equal to the cumulative volume fraction of the penetrated interspaces ranging from the largest interspaces $R_{eq,max}$, to the smallest penetrated ones $R_{eq,P}$. If the fibre over-crossing sites are treated as individual interspaces, the cumulative volume fraction of the infiltrated interspaces, i.e., $S(P_{inf})$ can be approximately given as follows with an assumption of a statistically uniform distribution of all the interspaces in the preform [3]:

$$S(P_{inf}) = \int_{R_{eq,P}}^{R_{eq,max}} V(R_{eq}) dR_{eq} = \frac{(1 - V_f)}{R_{eq,max}^3} [R_{eq,max}^3 - R_{eq,P}^3(P_{inf})] \quad (3)$$

As mentioned, the local infiltration pressure changes in the partially infiltrated preform in the infiltration direction. This pressure change will result in the variation of the degree of preform saturation dS/dz in the infiltration direction as follows [3]

$$\frac{dS}{dz} = \frac{A(1 - V_f)}{\sigma_{mg} \cos \theta R_{eq,max}^3} R_{eq,P}^4 \frac{dP}{dz} \quad (4)$$

According to the pressure distribution expressed in Eq. 1 and the relationship between saturation and local pressure in Eq. 3, the gradient of preform saturation in the infiltration direction dS/dz can be expressed as follows:

$$\frac{dS}{dz} = \frac{A\mu (1 - V_f) V_{Ram}}{D\sigma_{mg} \cos \theta R_{eq,max}} \cdot \frac{(R_{eq,P} / R_{eq,max})^4}{1 - (R_{eq,P} / R_{eq,max})^5} \quad (5)$$

As the above equation indicates, the gradient of preform saturation is a function of $(R_{eq,P} / R_{eq,max})^4 [1 - (R_{eq,P} / R_{eq,max})^5]^{-1}$. Fig. 3 illustrates the variation of the dS/dz with respect to the minimum dimension of the infiltrated interspaces.

Fig. 3 Effect of ϕ on η . Note the dramatic change of η at the infiltration front. (where, $\phi = (R_{eq,P} / R_{eq,max})$ and $\eta(R_{eq,P}) = (R_{eq,P} / R_{eq,max})^4 [1 - (R_{eq,P} / R_{eq,max})^5]^{-1}$).

Fig. 4 A schematic showing the volume distribution in a Saffil preform at the moment when the infiltration enters its air-compression stage. Where, S_{max} refers to the maximum saturation achievable, and $S_{max}(P_{pt})$ refers to the maximum saturation achieved under penetrating-through pressure P_{pt} .

As indicated by the figure, the preform saturation is very sensitive to the dimension of the newly infiltrated interspaces. The preform saturation is subjected to a dramatic change at the infiltration front, where $R_{eq.P} > 0.5 R_{eq.max}$, because the newly infiltrated large interspaces contribute significantly to the volume fraction of the infiltrated interspaces. However, after the passing-by of the infiltration front and the infiltration becomes stable, corresponding to the minimum dimension of infiltrated interspaces $R_{eq.P} < 0.5 R_{eq.max}$, the variation of saturation gradient becomes stable.

Before infiltration enters its air-compression stage signalled by the arrival of the infiltration front at the bottom of the preform, the saturation distribution of the preform along the infiltration direction is schematically shown in Fig. 4, which is consistent with the visualised saturation distribution [2].

The figure indicates that at the moment when melt penetrates through the preform, the volume of the un-infiltrated interspaces, occupied by the pre-existing air, mainly concentrates at the infiltration frontier. In the preform behind, where the infiltration pressure linearly increases from $2P_{cap.min}$ to P_{pt} --the penetrating-through pressure at the preform entry, the degree of the preform saturation correspondingly increases from $0.875(1-V_f)$ to $S(P_{pt})$ - the maximum degree of preform saturation achievable at the moment when melt penetrates through the preform under P_{pt} . However, as compared with the conventionally employed maximum squeeze pressure ranging from 50 to 130 MPa, P_{pt} has a very limited value ranging from ~1.0 to ~5.0 MPa for infiltration of 10-30% Saffil preform with speeds of less than 30 mm/s.

The above analysis clearly demonstrates that for infiltration in the atmosphere the air-entrapment is bound to happen on one hand, and indicates the existence of the potential to minimise the air entrapment by optimisation of the infiltration hydrodynamic parameters to reduce the length of infiltration front and to increase in penetrating-through pressure on the other hand.

Infiltration Speed and Air Entrapment

According to Eq. 1, an increase in infiltration speed will not only increase the pressure gradient in the preform and reduce the thickness of the infiltration front, but also gives rise to the value of the penetrating-through pressure. Correspondingly, the saturation of the preform is improved and the amount of the air entrapped and the frequency and dimension of the resultant non-infiltration defects are reduced.

The above analysis has made clear that the full saturation of the preform is not achievable, but the amount of the air entrapped in the preform can be changed by variation of the infiltration speed. Furthermore, as indicated by the above analysis, the maximum pressure conventionally quoted in squeeze pressure infiltration makes no contribution to the control of air-entrapment. Its significance on infiltration quality lies on the control of the size of non-infiltration defects caused by the entrapped air and capillarity, and on the enhancement of melt feeding capability to eliminate solidification shrinkage voids.

EFFECT OF INFILTRATION SPEED ON MICROSTRUCTURE AND TENSILE PROPERTIES

Processing of Saffil/AlCu4MgAg Composite

So far, the effect of infiltration speed on infiltration quality has been theoretically analysed in terms of preform saturation and, thereby, the amount of air entrapped. Obviously, an increase in air entrapment will be manifested as an increase in non-infiltration defects that degrade the soundness of the microstructure and mechanical performance of the material. To visualise this effect, Saffil chopped fibre preforms of 15% fibre volume fractions were squeeze infiltrated with AlCu4MgAg melt with a ram speed varying from 1.5 to 10 mm/s, but a constant maximum pressure of 130 MPa that was maintained until the completion of solidification post infiltration. The thermal processing parameters have been controlled constantly as: melt superheat of 750 °C, preform preheat of 650 °C, and ram and die preheat of 300 °C.

The composite castings produced with different infiltration speeds were subjected to a two step solution heat treatment (480 °C/2h + 500 °C/1.2h), followed by cold water quenching. Subsequently, the castings were aged to T4 (RT/1000h) and T6 (170 °C/4h) temper and machined into A₅ standard round bar dog bone tensile specimens with a gauge section geometry of $\phi 6 \times 36$ mm and tensile tested. Also, the microstructures in as-cast and heat-treated conditions were analysed by light microscopy and the tensile fractures were observed by scanning electron microscopy.

Effect on Tensile Properties

The tensile properties of the material under T4 and T6 conditions are given in Fig. 5a and Fig. 5b, respectively. It is evident that an increase in infiltration speed from 1.5 to 10 mm/s gives rise to the tensile strength from 378 MPa to 436 MPa, and the elongation from 1.6% to 4.6% under T4 condition. Under T6 condition, the tensile strength increases from 478 to 517 MPa, and the elongation from 1.2% to 2.0%, indicating the degradation of the infiltration quality and the resultant tensile properties with the decrease of infiltration speed.

Fig. 5a Effect of infiltration speed on T4 tensile properties of Saffil/AlCu4MgAg.

Fig. 5b Effect of infiltration speed on T6 tensile properties of Saffil/AlCu4MgAg.

Effect on Microstructure and Interfacial Bonding

Under high magnification, the existence of non-infiltration defects at fibre contact sites is obvious. However, the microstructures of the composite castings infiltrated with different speeds do not indicated any obvious difference on the dimension and frequency of the defects. The representative microstructures in the as-cast and T6 conditions are given in Fig. 6. Considering the 130 MPa maximum squeeze pressure employed and the existence of 5% porous SiO₂ fibre binder and the large number of fibre contact sites in the preform, it is not surprising that it is hard to note the difference under light microscope.

SEM observation of the tensile fractures, however, reveals the profound effect of the infiltration speed. As indicated by the fracture morphology in Fig. 7a, the material fabricated with high infiltration speed formed a strong fibre-matrix interface and the failure of the material is caused by fibre breakage and matrix shear failure. Consequently, the macro fracture of tensile specimens presents a 45° angle with the tensile direction and no fibre pull-out can be found, indicating a strong fibre-matrix bonding. The reduction of infiltration speed to 3 mm/s not only makes the macro fracture perpendicular to the tensile loading direction, but also characterises the micro fracture morphology by "fibre pull-out" and matrix necking, as shown in Fig. 7b. This fracture feature indicates that, before its final failure, the material was subjected a prevalent interfacial debonding, followed by matrix plastic necking during the tensile event.

Fig. 6a The representative micrograph of the as-cast 15% Saffil/AlCu4MgAg casting.

Fig. 6b The representative micrograph of the T6 15% Saffil/AlCu4MgAg casting.

Fig. 7a A fractograph of the T6 15% Saffil/AlCu4MgAg infiltrated with 10 mm/s speed.

Fig. 7b A fractograph of the T6 15% Saffil/AlCu4MgAg infiltrated with 3 mm/s speed.

Effect of Thermal Parameters

In the present work, effort has been concentrated on visualisation of the effect of the infiltration speed on the infiltration quality and mechanical performance under the thermal conditions that the infiltration is free of premature melt solidification. However, the present authors have experienced in processing instrumentation that the infiltration itself is not conducted under constant thermal conditions because the preform temperature and melt temperature will change dramatically during infiltration on the squeeze casters of industrial scale due to their heat loss prior to infiltration. A time delay during processing is able to induce adverse premature melt solidification that will degrade the infiltration hydrodynamics and impair the development of strong matrix-fibre bonding, resulting in poor mechanical performance [4]. Therefore, there will never be an over-emphasis on strict thermal management to actually control the thermal parameters within the optimal range to ensure infiltration free of premature melt solidification.

CONCLUSIONS

According to the above theoretical analysis and empirical investigation, it is clear that the air entrapment is inevitable in squeeze pressurised infiltration of fibre preforms in the atmosphere. The amount of the air entrapped is determined by the infiltration speed employed, the resultant pressure gradient in the infiltrated preform and the value of the penetrating-through pressure. The maximum pressure employed only functions to compress the entrapped air until it reaches a force balance with back pressure presented by the entrapped air and capillarity.

The entrapped air not only induces non-infiltration defects in the material, but also degrades the fibre-matrix interfacial bonding strength. Consequently, with decreased infiltration speed, the fabricated material will fail at reduced strength and elongation due to the low stress activation of non-infiltration defects and the interfacial debonding. To produce quality cast FMFCs, the infiltration speed should be maximised as far as the ultimate compression strength of the preform allows to minimise the amount of air entrapped.

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